

Rapid Synthesis of β -Lactams as Intermediates for Natural Products via Eco-friendly Reactions¹†

BIMAL K BANIK, MUTHUSWAMY JAYARAMAN, VAIDYANATHAN SRIRAJAN, MAGHAR S MANHAS and AJAY K BOSE*

Department of Chemistry and Chemical Biology, Stevens Institute of Technology, Hoboken, New Jersey 07030, U S A

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A variety of substituted β -lactams which serve as intermediates for diverse natural products have been prepared by rapid microwave assisted synthesis. Indium mediated reactions in aqueous media with azetidin-2,3-dione have been conducted in high yield to provide intermediates for pyrrolidine and piperidine alkaloids. The synthetic approaches reported here are more ecologically friendly than parallel conventional reactions described in the literature.

Synthetic organic chemistry is being redesigned by many research groups to make it more friendly to the environment. We discuss here some eco-friendly synthetic approaches that we have developed for the preparation of substituted β -lactams which serve as efficient synthons for antibiotics and anti-tumor compounds. We have devised 'Microwave-induced Organic Reaction Enhancement' (MORE) Chemistry techniques for conducting reactions with limited amounts of solvents (or no solvents) in open vessels in domestic microwave ovens. These techniques have been used in our laboratory for highly stereoselective and rapid synthesis of β -lactams and other heterocycles.

Safe and inexpensive MORE chemistry techniques

Microwave assisted organic chemistry is an emerging technology that is only ten years old. Discovery in 1986 of microwave assisted, highly accelerated, synthetic organic reactions in sealed vessels² (glass or special teflon) has led to sustained interest³ in the synthesis of various useful intermediates by using domestic microwave ovens. High pressures resulting from the rapid rise in temperature led to explosions in some cases². To avoid the risk of such explosions some laboratories have developed the use of solid phase reactions with substrates absorbed on clay, alumina, or silica gel. In contrast, we⁴ have developed techniques for conducting reactions in solution at ambient pressure using unmodified, commercial microwave ovens. The key features of our MORE chemistry methods are the use of limited amounts of high boiling solvents – enough to form a slurry at room temperature – and efficient control of microwave energy input to prevent the reaction mixture from boiling. Tall beakers topped by watch glasses or large conical flasks with funnels placed in their necks are convenient reaction vessels. Hydrocarbons and other nonpolar solvents absorb little microwave energy and are thus not suitable for MORE chemistry. Microwave energy entering the oven can be controlled by manipulating an on-off cycle of the microwave generator. Finer control is achieved readily by placing a

beaker of water (or DMF) as a heat sink near the reaction vessel in the microwave oven.

In previous publications, we⁵ have described simple techniques that are suitable for a variety of organic reactions on a small scale (a few mg) to medium size scale (a few hundred g). Reactions are conducted in a few minutes with complete safety. The selection of an efficient microwave energy transfer agent is very important. We have found that *N,N*-dimethylformamide (b.p. 154°), formamide (b.p. 216°), chlorobenzene (b.p. 154°), 1,2-dichlorobenzene (b.p. 180°), triglyme (b.p. 216°), 1,2-dichloroethane (b.p. 83°), and ethylene glycol (b.p. 196°) are excellent microwave energy transfer agents for a variety of organic reactions. Since polar molecules and salts absorb microwave energy directly there is no need for use of standard organic chemistry laboratory apparatus such as condensers, ground glass equipment, stirrers, heating mantles, oil-baths, water separators, etc.

Simplified catalytic transfer hydrogenation

The convenience and simplicity of MORE chemistry techniques are illustrated by the standard process in our laboratory now for rapid and highly efficient reduction or hydrogenolysis. The usual catalyst (10% Pd/C or commercial Raney nickel) is placed in an Erlenmeyer flask as a slurry with ethylene glycol; the compound to be reduced is added next followed by the addition of ammonium formate (the source of hydrogen). Irradiation in a domestic microwave oven for a few minutes so as to reach a temperature of 120–130° for the reaction mixture is adequate for complete hydrogenation (or hydrogenolysis). The choice of the catalyst can allow some selectivity⁶ as shown by the examples described in Schemes 1 and 2.

Scheme 1

†Dedicated to Professor T. R. Govindachari on the occasion of his 80th birthday.

Scheme 2

We have made extensive use of this reduction technique⁷ for preparing useful intermediates from α -vinyl- β -lactams (1) and β -styryl- β -lactams (2) as described in our recent publications^{6,8}.

Additional examples are provided in later sections of this review.

Stereocontrolled synthesis of α -hydroxy- β -lactams

We⁹ have shown that substituted β -lactams are efficient synthons for diverse natural products including amino sugars, higher sugars, amino acids and several types of antibiotics. Easy access to various optically pure α -hydroxy- β -lactam synthons by using MORE chemistry is discussed below.

Enantiospecific synthesis of α -hydroxy- β -lactams :

Schiff bases derived from an optically active α -hydroxy-aldehyde and an achiral amine have been found to provide optically pure *cis*- β -lactams¹⁰ upon reaction with alkoxy, aryloxy or acetoxyacetyl chloride and a tertiary amine. In a one-pot variant of this approach, we¹¹ prepared D-glyceraldehyde acetonide (4) by the oxidation of an aqueous solution of D-mannitol diacetonide (3) with sodium periodate and converted it *in situ* to Schiff bases 5 by reaction with various aromatic amines (Scheme 3). Enantiopure α -benzyloxy- β -lactams (6) was prepared by irradiating an ethylene dichloride solution of the Schiff base 5, benzyloxyacetyl chloride and triethylamine. Catalytic transfer hydrogenation

Ar = (a) *p*-anisyl, (b) benzyl (c) *p*-tolyl, (d) phenyl
Bn = OCH₂Ph, MWI* = microwave irradiation

Scheme 3

tion of the benzyloxy group in a microwave oven with ammonium formate and 10% Pd-C gave α -hydroxy- β -lactam (7) in excellent yield. Under identical conditions Raney Ni failed to give the desired product.

Reactions using MORE chemistry techniques can be completed on several hundred gram scale in about 10 min in an unmodified domestic microwave oven. We¹¹ have prepared 25 g of optically pure 7b in just one day by starting with mannitol diacetonide (which is commercially available).

MORE chemistry for stereocontrolled β -lactam formation

For a study of the effect of microwave irradiation on the formation of racemic α -hydroxy- β -lactam derivatives, we selected several Schiff bases of varying structures. Higher boiling chlorobenzene and *N*-methylmorpholine were chosen as the solvent and the base respectively. It was found that *trans*- β -lactam formation was favored at high power of microwave irradiation¹². In a recent publication, Endo and Droghini¹³ reported the formation of a *trans*- β -lactam by the slow addition of triethylamine to a refluxing solution of a Schiff base and an acid chloride in toluene solution. We¹² conducted this reaction in a microwave oven using chlorobenzene as the solvent at about 110° and observed that the ratio of *trans*-8 to *cis*- β -lactam 9 was \approx 90/10, irrespective of the sequence of addition of the reactants. We also demonstrated that this is not a base-catalyzed isomerization of the *cis*-compound to the thermodynamically more stable *trans*-isomer 8 at high temperature. It is worth noting that 6b is obtained as the *cis*-isomer even at high levels of microwave irradiation (Scheme 4). We had discovered earlier¹⁴ that the sequence of addition of the reactants play an important role in controlling the stereochemistry of the β -lactam. Under microwave irradiation, however, the sequence of addition is unimportant.

- (a) Ar = *p*-anisyl (*t/c* = 95/5)
(b) Ar = 3,4-dimethoxybenzyl (*t/c* = 90/10)
(c) Ar = benzyl (*t/c* = 90/10)
(d) Ar = phenyl (*t/c* = 90/10) *trans* isomer (8)
(e) Ar = methyl (*t/c* = 95/5) *cis* isomer (9)

Scheme 4

Optically pure α -hydroxy- β -lactams as synthons for taxol and analogs :

Taxol and its analogs have shown great promise as drugs for cancer chemotherapy¹⁵. Extensive structure-activity relationship studies have established that the phenyl isoserine side-chain at C-13 is crucial for biological activity. Coupling reaction¹⁵ of baccatin III and a protected derivative of (3*R*, 4*S*)-3-hydroxy-4-phenyl-2-azetidinone has been used

by several groups for the semisynthesis of taxol and analogs.

We^{16,17} prepared the four isomers of α -hydroxy- β -lactams related to the taxol side-chain and analogs via the Ferrier rearrangement¹⁸. Treatment of racemic β -lactam (10) with 3,4-di-*O*-acetyl-D-glucal (11) in the presence of iodine^{16,19} gave two separable diastereomeric glycosides

12 and 13 (Scheme 5). The stereochemistry of the glycoside bond was found to be α based on the coupling constant²⁰ of the anomeric hydrogen of the reduced product formed by catalytic transfer hydrogenation of 13 (Scheme 6). Mild acidic hydrolysis of the carbohydrate moiety in 12 and 13 produced enantiomerically pure α -hydroxy- β -lactams 14 and 16 respectively. Nmr studies on the acetates

15 and 17 in the presence of a chiral shift reagent and optical rotation of 14 and 16 established their absolute configuration.

Attempted reaction of racemic *trans*- β -lactams (18) with 11 under identical conditions failed to produce any glycoside. However, rhamnol diacetate (19) with racemic 18 gave two α -glycosides 20 and 21 which were individually converted to the optically pure antipodal pair 22 and 23 and the corresponding acetates 24 and 25 (Scheme 7).

Stereocontrolled synthesis of α -amino- β -lactams

In the earliest stage of our development of MORE chemistry techniques we found it possible to phthaloylate various amino acids on the millimolar scale in 2–3 min in a domestic microwave oven. Optically active amino acids were not racemized during this derivatization process. Recently we²¹ have reported a variation of this process that provides a very convenient access to α -amino- β -lactams which are well known intermediates²² for a variety of antibiotics, such as penicillins, cephalosporins, nocardicins, and monobactams.

Tetrachlorophthaloylglycine (27) can be prepared on 1–2 g scale in 90 s by irradiating a slurry of glycine, tetrachlorophthalic anhydride (26), and *N*-methylmorpholine in a small amount of DMF. The yield of the protected glycine was more than 90% (Scheme 8).

We have conducted the preparation of 27 on a molar scale in the same yield by irradiating the reaction mixture for about 8 min.

The acid chloride 28 was prepared from 27 in nearly quantitative yield by the action of thionyl chloride. A comparison was made of the yield and stereochemistry of the α -imido- β -lactams 29a and 29b prepared by the reaction of 28 with various Schiff bases when the cycloaddition was conducted under classical conditions and under microwave irradiation. Reaction at room temperature or lower in methylene chloride solution in presence of triethylamine gave a mixture of *cis*- and *trans*- β -lactams 29 (R = Ph) in comparatively low yield (Scheme 9). Next, microwave irradiation at high power was used to heat a chlorobenzene solution of the imine component and *N*-methylmorpholine to reach a temperature of about 100° when 28 was added rapidly. Upon further irradiation for about 3 min at low power, the reaction mixture was allowed to cool down when crystals of the product started to separate. Under these conditions the *trans*- β -lactam (29b, R = Ph) was the only pro-

duct. However, when an imine derived from cinnamaldehyde and *p*-anisidine was subjected to reaction under microwave irradiation, the *cis*- β -lactam (29a, R = styryl) was obtained exclusively at all power levels.

Scheme 9

The deprotection of the tetrachlorophthalimido group to obtain α -amino- β -lactams can be conducted in a few minutes on adding ethylenediamine and irradiating in a microwave oven. A number of 3-amino-2-azetidinones (30) were prepared in good yields by this procedure (Scheme 10).

Scheme 10

Controlling pollution at the source

Glass is essentially transparent to microwaves. Therefore, irradiation of a reaction mixture in a microwave oven allows transmission of energy directly to the reacting molecules. If the reactants are polar and absorb microwaves efficiently, a polar solvent is not needed as a microwave energy transfer agent (or reaction medium). Even when it is necessary to have a solvent present, only small amounts of the solvent are adequate as we have shown.

Solventless reactions :

In one of our earlier publications²³ we reported a successful solid phase reaction conducted in a microwave oven. The dehydration of the tertiary alcohol 31 to a natural product 32 was achieved in high yield in a 'dry reaction' when 31 deposited on silica gel was irradiated for about 10 min (Scheme 11).

Scheme 11

Previous workers have shown that the reagents adsorbed on montmorillonite KSF clay undergo efficient reactions on microwave irradiation even though the clay by itself does not absorb microwaves. In recent publications, Varma *et al.*²⁴ have reported that montmorillonite KSF clay can act as a 'catalyst' in some condensation reactions in the absence of any solvent. Such 'dry reactions' are conducted by them on a millimolar scale in test tubes placed in an alumina bath in a domestic microwave oven. Their method for

preparing imines was of much interest to us for the synthesis of β -lactams.

Our preliminary studies indicate that Schiff base formation on several gram scale can be achieved in a few minutes by irradiating an equimolar mixture of an aromatic aldehyde and an amine and 20% by weight of montmorillonite KSF clay. The Schiff base is formed in nearly quantitative yield. We have combined this solventless reaction with the next step in our synthesis to conduct a one-pot preparation of β -lactams (Scheme 12).

Scheme 12

On the basis of limited experimentation it appears that chlorobenzene as a reaction medium could be replaced totally or partly by anisole. Being free from halogen, anisole is a more eco-friendly solvent.

Organometallic reactions in aqueous media :

Recent publications have demonstrated that organometallic reactions of indium can be conducted successfully in aqueous media due to the unusual stability of the metal to water and air. Such reactions are of much current interest because of reduced potential of aqueous media for producing pollutions.

In preliminary studies we²⁵ have allowed allyl bromide and indium to react with azetin-2,3-diones (33) in water/tetrahydrofuran mixtures. The reaction product of 34 was a single product in about 80% yield. On the basis of ¹H nmr spectra it was possible to assign the configuration of 34 as *Z* (i.e. the aryl group and the hydroxyl group are *cis* to each other). The organoindium group appears to favor strongly the approach of the reagent to the C-3 carbonyl group of the azetin-2,3-dione from the face opposite to that containing the C-4 aryl group. When crotyl bromide was used in place of allyl bromide, the reaction was similar except for the introduction of an additional chiral center in the side-chain at C-3 of the β -lactam. The hydroxy group at C-3 was again found to be *cis* to the aryl group at C-4.

We have shown previously²⁶ that α -allyl- β -lactams are convenient intermediates for pyrrolidine and piperidine alkaloids via scission of the β -lactam ring and molecular rearrangement.

Scheme 13

Concluding remarks

Domestic microwave ovens are now standard equipment

in our research and teaching laboratories. These ovens are relatively inexpensive, safe, and easy to transport from one place to another. MORE chemistry techniques²⁷ allow the use of simple equipment for conducting organic reactions in a few minutes that can interest even high school students. We have created for Kemtec Educational Corporation a 'Microwave Instant Lab™' which can be used for providing hands-on laboratory training very inexpensively in high schools and undergraduate colleges that lack adequate facilities.

It is not clear yet whether microwave irradiation produces specific activation of any organic reaction. Nonetheless, microwave assisted chemistry reduces the requirement of solvents and leads to purer reaction products (for example, by creating less quantities of unwanted isomers through increased stereocontrol of reactions). Such processes strongly favor 'atom economy', that is, lead to high yields of the target compounds and small quantities of waste solvents, used chromatographic material, and unwanted byproducts. The pharmaceutical and fine chemical industries are, however, in a position now to benefit from microwave assisted chemistry.

It can be expected that the second decade of microwave chemistry will witness increasing use of environmentally benign synthetic processes that depend on MORE chemistry techniques and other microwave assisted chemical procedures.

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